

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 11

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“DANCE OF THE LIVING SOUL”

Gently it captures beauty within its beauty
That the living soul finds way to uncertainty
Where cellos and trombones heard from far away
To the spine and sensory deliverance to clarity

What it takes to dance for survival
Where narrow space couldn't do contouring climbs
Constraints suddenly gallop the ways
With cleverness where stance may get its way

Driven with the agile spirit
Believing in its ways to balance awkwardness
Dynamically progressive the way it is
Belief and certainty bring peace.

In every arch of the spine, artistic lines arise
Swaying limbs find proportion with quiet grace
Each rhythmic pulse measures distance slipping away
Cleverness, fused with spirit, moves beyond limits.

I wish each stride could move mountains
Today, tomorrow not far away from within
For the soul that longs for a happy ending
Ambiguity never comes again.